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Abstract	The progress report presents the summary of developments and preliminary results related to Task 4.1.

History of Changes

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0.1 (draft)	01 June 2025	The initial draft of the document is ready and ready for distribution between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
V0.5	25 June 2025	Final draft ready to be reviewed
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Executive summary

Deliverable D4.1 outlines the core developments related to autonomous exploration, path planning, and multi-machine coordination in underground mining environments. At the heart of this work is the design and implementation of a tailored autonomy framework, known as STAGE [1], which has been specifically adapted to operate under the spatial, perceptual, and communication constraints typical of deep and abandoned mines. This deliverable introduces a novel planning pipeline that enables robots to explore unknown environments incrementally while building and updating a topological graph representation of the area. The system operates solely using onboard sensors and local computation, without relying on any external infrastructure. Using the STAGE autonomy stack, robots can identify exploration frontiers, generate safe motion plans, and autonomously expand the shared map of the environment.

A key aspect of the work focuses on multi-machine coordination. The deliverable describes how robots share their occupancy maps and graph structures, enabling downstream tasks such as handover between robots. For example, an explorer robot that has mapped part of a mine can transmit its local map and topological graph to a deployer robot, which can then continue its own mission using this prior knowledge. This forms a critical bridge toward the alignment and deployment tasks in Task 4.2. The document also introduces initial work on conflict-aware path planning, addressing the challenge of coordinating multiple robots that may operate in overlapping spaces. This work explores how planning can incorporate information about other agents' current and future positions to avoid deadlocks, congestion, or unsafe proximity in narrow corridors.

These capabilities collectively advance the autonomy required for scalable, infrastructure-free multi-robot operations in subterranean settings and lay the groundwork for field testing and system-wide integration in subsequent work packages.

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2 Introduction

Autonomous robotic operation in deep and abandoned mining environments poses a range of unique challenges, from degraded perception conditions and limited communication infrastructure to highly constrained operational spaces. These subterranean settings are often structurally complex, unpredictable, and inherently hazardous for human intervention. As such, they present a compelling case for the development of fully autonomous systems that can safely and efficiently explore, map, and operate in these environments with minimal supervision.

Task 4.1 addresses this challenge by developing and validating autonomous path planning algorithms and multi-machine coordination strategies tailored to underground mining scenarios. Rather than relying on traditional GPS-based or infrastructure-supported navigation systems, the focus is placed on robust, infrastructure-free autonomy powered by onboard sensing and local computation. The task aims to equip autonomous mining machines with the ability to plan paths through previously unknown or partially known environments, dynamically update their understanding of the space, and coordinate their actions with other machines operating in the same vicinity.

One of the central outcomes of this task is the development of the STAGE autonomy framework, a flexible behavior-based planning system designed to scale across multiple agents while operating under resource constraints typical of underground missions. STAGE provides the logic and architecture needed to support modular decision-making, situational awareness, and role allocation among heterogeneous agents. The framework is developed with long-term system deployment in mind and is being iteratively tested and refined in simulated mine environments. In addition to individual navigation capabilities, this deliverable introduces foundational mechanisms for multi-machine coordination, including the sharing of occupancy maps and topological graphs. This allows robots to build and benefit from a shared understanding of the environment, enabling downstream collaboration, such as mission handover between explorer and deployer machines. Furthermore, the document discusses the early stages of conflict-aware planning, a critical requirement for ensuring safety and efficiency when multiple autonomous agents navigate overlapping spaces.

This introduction sets the stage for the more detailed discussions that follow, which elaborate on the architectural decisions, planning algorithms, simulation environments, and coordination logic developed to date. The work presented here serves as the foundation for future integration and field deployment efforts within the broader context of the project.

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

This deliverable, D4.1, presents the current progress under Task 4.1 – Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination, within the context of autonomous operations in deep and abandoned mining environments. The primary aim of this document is to detail the design and initial validation of novel path planning algorithms and coordination strategies for multiple autonomous mining machines hereafter referred to as *machines*. These capabilities are essential enablers for realizing fully autonomous exploration, drilling, and excavation operations in challenging underground environments where human access is either unsafe or impossible.

This is an intermediate technical report reflecting progress achieved midway through the task duration (M5–M18). It focuses on the algorithmic design, simulation-based validation, and integration strategies developed so far, particularly with respect to robust autonomous navigation in unknown or partially known spaces, information exchange between machines, and initial coordination logic for multi-machine operations.

The document introduces a graph-based path planning method designed for operation in dynamically evolving subterranean spaces, as well as early coordination strategies for safe and efficient machine-to-machine navigation. While not all developments have reached deployment-ready maturity, the results outlined demonstrate meaningful steps toward the project's long-term goals.

2.2 Related documents

This deliverable is complemented by the technical specifications and architecture definitions from earlier work packages, particularly those focused on system design, sensor integration, and machine architecture. The algorithms described herein are developed to be compatible with the modular software and communication architecture envisioned in the project and will evolve further based on findings from upcoming field validation and integration activities.

Machines Terminology:

- Explorer --> Machine 1 that autonomously explores and maps the unknown environment.
- Deployer --> Machine 2 that oversees autonomously navigating to area of interest (mine face) based on received information from Explorer machine.
- Supplier --> Machine 3 that brings reinforcements and additional robots such as the stinger robot to the mine face ahead of the deployment.

3 Technical details

3.1 Novel path planning algorithm for autonomous exploration and mapping of unknown deep and abandoned mines

Modern underground mining operations are evolving towards automation, not just to improve productivity, but also to significantly enhance safety by reducing human presence in high-risk zones. Deep and abandoned mines, often lacking any form of digital infrastructure, present a particularly challenging environment for autonomous operation. Within such domains, autonomous machines must independently navigate complex, narrow, and often unknown networks of tunnels, respond to environmental uncertainty, and coordinate with other machines sharing the same operational area.

This task addresses these needs by laying the groundwork for intelligent navigation and coordination capabilities in such conditions. Our motivation stems from three key challenges:

- 1. Autonomous navigation in dynamic and constrained environments**
Machines must be capable of navigating to operational targets such as active mine faces or dumping stations through environments that are continuously mapped and updated during operation. This requires path planners that are robust to both environmental change and initial lack of information.
- 2. Coordination of multiple machines with overlapping operational goals**
Mining operations frequently involve several autonomous machines working in proximity. Preventing congestion, collision, and deadlock is vital for uninterrupted and efficient operation. This demands coordination algorithms that consider both spatial and temporal conflict resolution.
- 3. Elimination of reliance on external infrastructure**
The envisioned system operates without fixed infrastructure such as GPS, Wi-Fi beacons, or pre-installed maps. All decision-making and coordination must therefore emerge from onboard sensing, peer-to-peer communication, and distributed planning logic.

In this document, we present initial progress toward addressing these challenges. The STAGE planner, developed by LTU, is introduced as a core component of the path planning module, enabling robust exploration and navigation in dynamic 3D environments. The planner incrementally builds a spatial graph representation of the mine, dynamically updates it as new information becomes available, and enables navigation to arbitrary waypoints such as mine faces. Early developments in conflict-based planning for multiple machines and inter-machine information sharing protocols are also documented, forming the foundation for the coordination framework to be expanded in the next phase of the project.

In the context of autonomous operations in subterranean mines, path planning solutions must address several critical challenges: constrained topologies, dynamic scene changes, lack of external infrastructure, and the need for scalable long-duration autonomy. To meet these requirements, we have developed a novel graph-based navigation framework called STAGE (Scalable and Traversability-Aware Graph-based Exploration), specifically tailored to dynamic and infrastructure-free environments like deep mines.

3.1.1 STAGE Planner Design Principles

The STAGE planner is designed around the core insight that both *local responsiveness* and *global consistency* are essential for efficient exploration and mission continuity in unknown underground environments. Traditional exploration planners tend to either focus on small-scale, reactive frontier navigation or global graph-based planning that assumes a static world. STAGE addresses this gap by introducing a two-layer graph structure that allows for both scalable planning and robustness to environment changes. Please refer to Figure 1 for visual representation of the algorithm workflow of the STAGE planner.

Dual Graph Representation:

The planner builds and maintains two distinct graph layers:

1. **Local Sub-Graphs:** These are built in real-time using direct point cloud visibility from the robot's onboard sensors. They identify *frontier nodes* regions at the boundary of known and unknown space with high volumetric exploration gain. These graphs guide the robot towards locally informative areas quickly and efficiently.
2. **Global Graph:** A higher-level representation is incrementally constructed by stitching together overlapping local sub-graphs. This allows the robot to re-use previously mapped areas for global repositioning, without redundant reprocessing. The overlap detection and edge formation are highly memory- and computation-efficient, enabling continuous long-term operation.

Traversability-Awareness and Scene Adaptation:

Unlike conventional planners that assume static maps once constructed, STAGE explicitly addresses scene changes a common occurrence in operational mines (e.g., blocked tunnels, moving equipment). During global navigation, each planned path is divided into adaptive segments. These are validated using a visibility-constrained oriented sampling space, allowing the planner to detect new obstacles before collision occurs. If a segment is deemed untraversable, it is discarded, and an alternate path is dynamically re-planned, using updated map information.

This mechanism ensures robust exploration continuity, even when environmental conditions evolve over time or obstacles emerge in previously safe zones.

Figure 1: Sequential visualization of the STAGE planner's exploration and global graph construction behavior.

Simulation and Experimental Validation:

The STAGE planner has been evaluated in both simulation and real-world scenarios:

- Simulation tests used aerial robots exploring complex cave-like environments featuring narrow passages and wide voids.
- Field tests were conducted using a Boston Dynamics Spot robot equipped with 3D LiDAR and RGB-D sensors, navigating university underground corridors to simulate mine-like conditions.

In both cases, the planner successfully demonstrated:

- High exploration coverage
- Efficient handling of blocked paths
- Minimal CPU usage compared to state-of-the-art methods (notably the GBP planner)

A key finding was STAGE's ability to reposition the robot autonomously to alternative frontiers after a global path was rendered invalid due to a sudden obstacle (e.g., closed door), showcasing its core value in dynamic environments.

Relevance to the Project Objectives:

The STAGE planner fulfills critical technological needs for the autonomous machines (Explorer, Deployer, Supplier) described in this project:

- Enables infrastructure-free navigation toward mission-critical waypoints (e.g., mine faces)
- Supports exploration and re-positioning within dynamic subterranean networks
- Lays the foundation for conflict-aware multi-machine coordination by offering predictable and adaptive navigation paths

As part of this deliverable, we report the integration of STAGE into the autonomy stack of the *Explorer machine*. Future work includes extending its use to coordination contexts, where machine-to-machine planning and conflict resolution are required.

3.1.2 Simulation Environment for Autonomous Mine Navigation and Exploration

To support the development and validation of the STAGE planner in a representative and realistic underground environment, a dedicated simulation pipeline was established within the ROS 2 and Ignition Gazebo ecosystem. This integration enables full-stack autonomy testing and benchmarking in a safe and repeatable manner, without requiring immediate deployment in physical mines.

As part of this effort, we collaborated with our industrial partner Grecian Magnesite (GM), who provided detailed LAS-format 3D point cloud data from both the active production areas and the abandoned sectors of one of their mines (ref. Figure 2). These high-fidelity datasets form the basis for constructing simulation environments that closely resemble the operational conditions and spatial constraints encountered by autonomous machines during real missions.

Figure 2: The original LAS scan from the GM mine is converted into a mesh format for further integration into gazebo as a simulation world.

The LAS point clouds were processed and converted into 3D mesh models, accurately representing the geometry of the underground corridors, tunnels, and void spaces. These meshes were subsequently integrated into Ignition Gazebo simulation worlds, where virtual ground robots representing the project's *Explorer*, *Deployer*, and *Supplier* machines can be deployed for mission trials.

Figure 3: The imported GM mine as simulation world in the gazebo simulator. The textures and colors are ignored for simplicity.

In this simulated environment, the STAGE planner is responsible for:

- Autonomous exploration of unknown areas
- Dynamic navigation to mine face waypoints
- Handling blockages and re-routing in real-time using simulated changes to the environment

This setup provides a valuable bridge between algorithmic development and real-world deployment, allowing for robust pre-validation of navigation capabilities under realistic mine-like conditions before transitioning to hardware testing in the field.

The core functionality of the STAGE planner lies in its ability to incrementally construct a dense local graph from sensor observations and to select a safe and information-rich path for autonomous exploration. This is achieved through a tightly integrated perception-to-planning loop that leverages direct point cloud visibility, local frontier detection, and information-theoretic sampling for goal selection.

At each planning iteration, the machine acquires a dense 3D point cloud from onboard sensors (e.g., LiDAR or RGB-D), as shown in Figure 4-a. This point cloud is projected into a local occupancy map, which is then processed to extract *frontier voxels* regions that border between known free space and unexplored (unknown) areas. Around the robot's current position, the planner defines a sampling space bounded by the visibility volume of the current scan. Within this space, a set of candidate positions (nodes) are sampled for potential exploration goals.

Figure 4 : Visualization of the local planning process of the STAGE planner.

Each sampled node is evaluated based on its volumetric information gain, i.e., the number of unknown voxels it would expose if visited. This metric captures the expected benefit of visiting that location in terms of expanding the known environment.

Figure 5: Execution aware refinement of the exploration path based on operational constraints.

To assist in visualization and debugging, the nodes are color-coded according to their computed gain ranging from red (high gain) to purple (low gain), as seen in Figure 4-b.

Once gain scores are assigned, the nodes are interconnected to form a local sub-graph. Edge connections are created based on traversability and proximity, and the resulting graph encodes all viable routes within the sampled space. Using Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm, the planner computes paths from the robot's current position (graph root) to all reachable nodes in the sub-graph.

From these candidate paths, the node with the highest combined exploration reward (accounting for gain and heading penalty) is selected as the target for local exploration. The initial path, shown in red in Figure 4-c, represents the shortest route to that goal through the local graph.

To ensure real-world feasibility, the selected path is subjected to an adaptive refinement step. This accounts for the machine's locomotion model, terrain constraints, and obstacle margins. The result is a refined local exploration path, shown in green in Figure 5-a, which is safe for execution given the machine's capabilities. The refinement process also filters out paths that might enter marginally observed or untraversable areas and instead promotes smoother, shorter, and safer alternatives. This step is critical for achieving robust autonomy in subterranean environments where visibility is often limited and terrain may rapidly change.

Figure 5-b and 5-c further illustrate alternate views of the sampled nodes and local graph structure, reinforcing the planner's reliance on visibility-constrained sampling and gain-based goal selection.

Through this structured, layered approach, the STAGE planner ensures that each navigation decision is grounded in both perceptual reality and mission-driven value, enabling machines to explore efficiently and safely in complex, unknown mines.

3.1.3 Incremental Autonomous Mapping of GM Mine Simulation Environment

To evaluate the real-time performance and robustness of the STAGE planner in realistic underground settings, we conducted autonomous exploration trials using the converted 3D mesh of the Grecian Magnesite (GM) mine within the Ignition Gazebo simulation environment. These experiments were designed to simulate the mapping of previously unknown or abandoned areas of the mine using only onboard sensors and autonomy logic.

Figure 6: Snapshots from an autonomous exploration mission using the STAGE planner in the Grecian Magnesite (GM) mine simulation world (early phase). The machine begins to map its immediate surroundings, incrementally extending its explored area through local frontier navigation.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 showcase a series of snapshots captured at regular time intervals during a single autonomous mission. The images visualize the incrementally built map as perceived by the robot while navigating and exploring the underground tunnels. The coloring encodes traversal progression, with each panel highlighting the evolving coverage as the robot explores further into the mine's interior.

The exploration strategy employed here is a hallmark of the STAGE planner's design: a bifurcated local-global exploration framework. The machine first builds local sub-graphs based on its real-time point cloud, using these to select and execute short-term exploration paths toward high-gain frontiers. However, once local exploration converges either due to a dead-end, low information gain, or visibility constraints the planner shifts into global re-positioning mode.

In this mode, the robot queries a global graph that encodes all previously explored frontiers and the interconnecting pathways between them. Using this structure, the robot computes global Dijkstra paths to reposition itself toward a distant, still-unexplored region of the mine what we refer to as a global frontier.

This alternation between focused local exploration and informed global repositioning ensures that the robot avoids becoming trapped in isolated areas, and instead steadily pushes the exploration boundary outward. The result is a highly efficient and autonomous mapping of large-scale, complex subterranean spaces, as demonstrated in the final frames of Figure 7, where the robot has covered a large, bifurcated region of the simulated mine.

Figure 7: Continued progression of the mission, showing large-scale mapping of the mine. As local frontiers become exhausted, the robot repositions to unexplored global frontiers via the global graph, resulting in bifurcated exploration patterns that maximize spatial coverage and information gain.

Figure 8 : Incremental autonomous mapping of the abandoned section of the Grecian Magnesite (GM) mine using the STAGE planner. The sequence (bottom to top) shows the evolution of the robot's internal map as it explores the environment from a fixed starting point. The robot begins with minimal knowledge of its surroundings and progressively uncovers complex tunnel structures through local exploration and global repositioning. This figure highlights the planner's ability to autonomously and efficiently explore large-scale subterranean environments while maintaining spatial coherence and resilience in unstructured settings.

Figure 8 further demonstrates the STAGE planner's capability for fully autonomous exploration and mapping in large, unknown environments. In this experiment, the robot begins at a fixed start location within the abandoned section of the Grecian Magnesite (GM) mine, with no prior map information. From bottom to top, the snapshots depict the incremental evolution of the robot's internal map, captured at regular intervals during the mission. The early frames show limited spatial awareness, while the upper frames highlight the culmination of extensive exploration, covering wide bifurcating branches of the mine. This progression illustrates not only the planner's local and global exploration strategy, but also its resilience and autonomy capable of persistently expanding knowledge without human input, even in highly unstructured and GPS-denied environments.

Figure 9: Visualization of the robot's current position and LiDAR scan during autonomous exploration of the GM mine simulation world. The colored point cloud shows the latest scan overlaid on the global map, emphasizing the robot's live perception and position tracking within the growing mapped environment.

3.1.4 Final Remarks on Autonomous Exploration and Implications for Multi-Machine Coordination

The performance of the STAGE planner in the large-scale Grecian Magnesite (GM) mine simulation environment illustrates the maturity and robustness of our autonomous exploration pipeline. The two results presented in Figure 9 and Figure 10 encapsulate the planner's end-to-end autonomy in a complex subterranean setting. In Figure 9, the currently acquired LiDAR scan (highlighted

in color) is shown overlaid on the accumulated surface point cloud map, visualizing the robot's present location in relation to the already explored mine. This real-time overlay demonstrates the planner's ability to incrementally build and maintain a globally consistent map while operating entirely without external infrastructure.

Figure 10: Final accumulated surface point cloud map of the GM mine after a full autonomous exploration mission using the STAGE planner. The result highlights the planner's capability to comprehensively explore complex, unstructured underground areas with no prior map, relying solely on onboard sensing and goal-aware planning.

In Figure 10, the final surface-level point cloud map is shown, capturing the full extent of the explored mine after a complete autonomous mission. The result demonstrates STAGE's capacity to enable a machine to systematically navigate and map either completely unknown or partially known environments, regardless of prior access or instrumentation.

This navigation autonomy is driven by the planner's core principle of goal-directed local graph exploration, combined with a memory-efficient global graph representation. Together, these allow the system to select high-gain local frontiers and re-position efficiently to distant, unexplored regions. Beyond standalone exploration, this architecture also provides a strong foundation for multi-machine coordination: the global graph and map generated by the *Explorer* machine are structured in a way that can be seamlessly shared with *Deployer* or *Supplier* machines, enabling collaborative planning, routing, and task execution in follow-up phases of operation.

In summary, the STAGE planner addresses the challenges of autonomous underground navigation with a scalable, traversability-aware solution that supports both exploration and strategic coordination in multi-agent scenarios.

3.2 Machine to machine information exchange

A key component of the STAGE planner's decision-making process is its method for selecting a single, high-quality exploration path from a dense set of local path candidates. After building a local sub-graph from visibility-based sampling (as described earlier), the planner computes shortest paths from the robot's current location to each local frontier node using Dijkstra's algorithm. These paths are visualized in Figure 11-a as the dense collection of pink trajectories extending forward from the robot's current position.

Figure 11 : (a) Dense local Dijkstra paths (in pink) computed from the robot to nearby frontier nodes. These are later clustered using dynamic time warping distances to identify a representative final exploration path. (b) Integration of the refined exploration path into the global graph. This global structure encodes the connectivity between explored and unexplored regions and is later shared with the Deployer machine for global route planning and navigation toward mission-critical areas such as mine faces.

However, rather than immediately committing to the shortest path, the planner takes an additional step to ensure that the selected exploration path is not only short but also representative of the overall structure of promising frontiers. To do this, the planner applies a clustering process to the local Dijkstra paths using Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) distances. DTW allows for meaningful comparison of path shapes, even when they vary slightly in length or structure. By clustering the paths and selecting a representative candidate, the planner ensures that the chosen route balances exploration reward with geometric reliability. This refined selection strategy plays a key role in improving local robustness especially in environments with complex geometry like multi-branch tunnels or high branching uncertainty.

Beyond local planning, STAGE also maintains a global graph representation that captures both the topological structure of the explored space and the history of discovered frontiers. This global graph is incrementally built by connecting local sub-graphs and continuously updated with information about blocked paths, traversable segments, and observed frontiers. It serves as a long-term memory of the robot's exploration effort and forms a critical backbone for multi-machine knowledge sharing within the project.

In particular, the global graph maintained by the Explorer machine will later be transmitted to the Deployer machine as part of the cooperative workflow defined in Task 4.2. Alongside the voxel-based map of the environment, the global graph will enable the Deployer to:

- Understand which regions of the mine have already been explored.
- Identify candidate mine faces or areas of interest.
- Plan a global route to navigate autonomously toward these targets.

This process exemplifies the handover of spatial knowledge between heterogeneous machines, where one machine explores and builds situational awareness, and another leverages this shared understanding for task-specific navigation and operation.

The bottom part of Figure 6-b shows this continuity in action, where the refined path is extended in the context of the global topology. It highlights how local planning decisions tie into the larger map representation supporting not just short-term movement, but long-term mission goals across multiple autonomous systems.

3.3 Conflict based path planning for multiple machines in tight spaces

In underground mining scenarios, the operational efficiency and safety of autonomous machines are critically dependent on effective conflict-free navigation and task assignments. Due to the constrained and narrow nature of mining tunnels, reversing maneuvers can be particularly challenging and inefficient. Thus, it is essential to plan coordinated paths that avoid collisions and

conflicts proactively while ensuring optimal task assignment and sequencing to maximize overall productivity.

Prerequisites:

To effectively implement conflict-based collaborative path planning, the following inputs are essential:

- **Map:** A detailed and accurate representation of the mine environment structured as a navigable graph (undirected graph with nodes and edges for path planning and 3D occupancy map for trajectory generation)
- **Agent Specifications:** Clear definitions of start position for each mining machine, along with physical size, operational speeds, and dynamic constraints.
- **Task Locations and Compatibility:** Defined task points that machines need to visit, along with compatibility criteria indicating which machine can perform specific tasks.

Figure 112 : The framework diagram of Coordinated Task Planning and Trajectory Generation

The overall framework for coordinated task planning and trajectory generation is illustrated in Figure 12. Given the initial positions of the robotic agents and a set of task locations in a known environment, the front-end of LTU developed system Conflict-Based Search with Task Sequencing (CBS-TS) computes a set of discrete, conflict-free paths for all agents. CBS-TS jointly performs task assignment, task sequencing, and multi-agent pathfinding to ensure all tasks are covered while minimizing overall flowtime. In the back end, each discrete path is temporally parameterized by assigning time intervals to individual path segments. These time-parameterized paths are then converted into smooth, dynamically feasible trajectories that can be safely executed by real robots. To ensure collision avoidance with static obstacles during this process, the trajectory generation is constrained within precomputed safe corridors, which bound the trajectory away from obstacle regions.

Specifically, CBS-TS begins by discretizing the workspace into a navigable graph. Initially, optimal paths and task sequences are independently computed for each

machine. However, potential conflicts, such as simultaneous occupation of the same location or traversal conflicts on paths, are identified during validation. Conflicts trigger the addition of constraints at the high-level planning stage. The CBS-TS algorithm iteratively resolves these conflicts by either adding new constraints or exploring other assignment alternatives, thereby selecting the paths and sequences without degradation in path optimality. Once CBS-TS generates discrete, conflict-free paths, they should be transformed into smooth and dynamically feasible trajectories for underground machines. Safe corridors, defined as convex regions around planned paths, are constructed to constrain trajectories within obstacle-free zones, accounting for the machine's size and safety margins. Trajectory optimization within these safe corridors incorporates dynamic feasibility constraints, including limits on acceleration, deceleration, and curvature. This ensures trajectories are realistic and executable by actual machines, preventing operational hazards and inefficiencies.

(a) Discrete paths from CBS-TS

(b) Safe corridor construction

(c) Trajectory generation

Figure 12 . Safe corridor construction and the trajectory optimization. Dashed lines denote the discrete paths generated from CBS-TS for these 2 robots 4 tasks case. Colored shaded squares are the safe corridor generated by expanding each segment of the path in xy axes until an obstacle

The proposed framework has been evaluated in an indoor environment of size 7m by 5m area. Two distinct environments were constructed: an unstructured layout with randomly placed obstacles of varying shapes, and a maze-like layout, seen in Figure 13. In both environments, a set of tasks was randomly distributed, drawn from three task types: tasks designated for TurtleBots (green dots), tasks designated for Unitree robots (blue dots), and tasks that could be handled by either platform (orange dots). And it can be seen from Figure 14 and Figure 15 that all the tasks can be handled by corresponding robots in sequence. The video demonstration of the experimental verification can be found at <https://youtu.be/j3UU694Ils0?si=gSPJu9t9n7wr2jU5>.

Figure 13. Top view of the physical environment

Figure 14. Assignment result and planned trajectory in unstructured environment

Figure 15. Assignment result and planned trajectory in maze-like environment

4 Partners Contributions:

Task 4.1 is led by the RAI team at Luleå University of Technology (LTU), who are responsible for the core development efforts. LTU's primary contribution focuses on advancing novel path planning algorithms for both known and unknown environments, enabling robust autonomous navigation under varying terrain and mission conditions. The Technical University of Denmark (DTU) team supports the task with two key contributions. First, DTU has conducted a literature review on multi-machine coordination strategies, helping to establish a theoretical foundation for collaborative autonomy. Second, DTU has developed a comprehensive simulation environment in ROS 2 using Ignition Gazebo. This environment includes a detailed model of a terrain hopper robot and is used for testing and validating autonomous mission scenarios in simulated conditions. Together, these complementary contributions form a strong foundation for the development and evaluation of autonomous multi-agent systems within the task. The contribution of MRP and EPI have been also valuable as part of high-level discussions on correctly drafting out core requirements of the exploration and planning system. UPAT have also contributed to discussions and to give feedback from the mechanical design of the system.

5 Future Plans

The next phase of development will focus on the hardware implementation and field testing of the STAGE autonomy framework. A key objective is to demonstrate multi-robot coordination with STAGE running simultaneously across several agents, all managed by a central base station capable of issuing mission commands, receiving status updates, and orchestrating distributed exploration and deployment activities.

This multi-agent deployment model will be tested during the September 2025 field trial at the GM mine site in Athens, where the full autonomy stack developed under Task 4.1 will be evaluated under real-world conditions. During this field trial, STAGE will be tested in scenarios involving both autonomous exploration and graph/map sharing between robots to enable mission continuation and flexible role assignment.

The outcome of this hardware evaluation will directly inform the continued development efforts within WP5, particularly for Tasks 5.2 and 5.5, which aim to scale the system across more agents and more complex, large-scale mine environments. Real-world testing and feedback from this deployment will be crucial in refining system robustness, mission flexibility, and coordination strategies required for full autonomy in production-scale subterranean applications.

6 Conclusions

D4.1 presents an integrated framework for autonomous exploration and coordination in underground mining environments. The STAGE autonomy framework developed in this task is capable of incrementally exploring unknown environments, constructing navigable topological graphs, and sharing this information with other machines in a scalable and robust way.

The autonomy system has been validated in a simulated GM mine environment, demonstrating the ability of robots to autonomously plan paths, update shared maps, and exchange mission-relevant information. Through this, the system enables not only solo exploration but also coordinated missions involving multiple heterogeneous agents.

Additionally, this deliverable introduces concepts for conflict-based planning, highlighting how multiple machines can operate safely and efficiently even when physical space is limited or access to shared resources (like tunnel sections) must be negotiated. The progress outlined in this deliverable establishes a solid foundation for enabling real-world deployment of multi-agent systems in unstructured, infrastructure-denied environments.

7 References

1. Patel, A., Saucedo, M. A. V., Kanellakis, C., & Nikolakopoulos, G. (2024). *STAGE: Scalable and Traversability-Aware Graph based Exploration Planner for Dynamically Varying Environments*. In *Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)* (pp. 5949–5955). IEEE.